

SITE SPHINX	DATE 25-26/VIII/80	AREA CHAPEL CAISSON	SQUARE	PAGE
	Coordinates: S INTERIOR WALL UNDER LARGE BLOCKS, AGAINST BEDROCK LEDGE		Levels	
			Top:	Bottom:
	TRIANGULAR SPACE		DIMENSIONS	
Feature No.	Diameter:	Width: .26 front .22 Back	Length: ^{36 cm} from edge adjacent block (E) to face of fill.	Depth: (height) 45 (front N) ≈ 30 Back (fill face)

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions	
1	SAND	BUFF-TAN	LOOSE	FINE	T / Small Frag Tiny Particles	Lm CHIPS	Gp
						Gr	Char ← Few small spots
						Do	
					D Δ	Ba	
						Al	
						Other Minute Grey Mud Spots	
2	CLAY	TAN-BROWN	COMPACT		T	Lm FRAGS SCATTERED	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba ← 1-2 Small CHIPS	
						Al	
						Other 17 SMALL ROUND FLAT BEADS VERY SMALL BONES (Bird Size)	
					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
					D	Ba	
						Al	
						Other	

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/	No./	B&W: Roll/	No./
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DRAWN	Area Plan:	Feature Plan:	Sections:
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: 25/VIII/80 Feature plotted in section 23. Block has fine join with large limestone block on E side. Join of lesser fineness w/ large overlying block. Space fist-sized, wide at top, between "plug" block and face of bedrock ledge at base of Sphinx chest forming W side interior of caisson. This space cleared by hand of fine sand sloping up to S inside of space around to inner back corner of plug block. More into space the sand becomes more humidified to a compact tan clay (2). Plug block separated from seam of adjacent large block to E w/ trowel blade, chisels pounded in. Same separation achieved w/ chisel, hammer in join to overlying block, and at contact point w/ sloping bedrock ledge → floor on lower W side corner. After 3 hours work, able to move block up and down w/ large crowbar. 26/VIII/80. Plug block gradually moved out by moving it up and down until it could be dragged out. Face of fill behind it looks to be compact tan clay (2). (REVERSE).

AFTER REMOVAL "PLUG BLOCK"

DIMENSIONS OF BLOCK:

Length .63 m.
Width .25 m protruding end
.27 m back end
Height
(Thickness) .22 m Back end
.26 m protruding end.

Slope from face of bedrock ledge to floor gradual forming a kind of hump. This also slopes up into feature space. Tan clay-moist, adhering to sides of block when it was stuck into fill. Block appears to be reused slop, similar to those used in finish (restoration?) work on PHASE I of body of Sphinx. w. a slight batter to one flat face (.22 m face). This has been roughly recut to make the plug block fit into sloping space as described, above between large overlying and adjacent blocks and bedrock ledge-floor.

— 26/VIII/80 10:00-12:30 am: CLAY-like sand fill taken out of space behind "plug" block position. to bedrock ledge running E-W at inner side of S forepaw. Fill contained loose scattered limestone frags (sharp) Dries out to more sandy. 1 large black (low fire) shard taken from recess cutting in behind large adjacent block to immediate E. Shard was wedged in against bedrock ledge between it and large limestone chip. Non diagnostic, surface outside worn away except small patch of crude red surface. Interior wall smooth and black. Also 1 faience round bead which broke in 2 pieces on removal in fill. CLAY clumps and sandy-clayey matrix sampled.

The large overlying block continues S-ward to rest partly on ledge (bedrock) running E-W. This ledge forms a kind of crude corner w/ bedrock ledge running N-S and appearing as W side lower part of crisson. At the corner the bedrock ledge cutting's face juts inward (W-ward) to form a recess about 10-15 cm wide w/ rounded edges. This is likely a natural recess perhaps due to a fault (note blocking against lower part of chest up above crisson's mod. cement cover - mod. blocking, as though recess-fault continues upward). The face of E-W part of ledge has a hole-like recess which looks fresh cut (white sharp angular on inside of round recess. This also like the chipping out of natural undulation or limestone recess.

Matrix fill, in 3 1/2 baskets, sifted up on cement cover of crisson after it was cleaned.

DIMENSIONS OF A1 SPACE AFTER EXCAVATION FILL

Length (from N. edge of large limestone block forming E side of space): .47 m.
(to E-W Bedrock ledge)
Width Back end along bedrock ledge (E-W) from edge of large limestone block forming E side of space to inside of recess at ledge corner: .47 m (top space)
Front end between limestone block and N-S ledge face, top of space: .35 m
.28 m (bottom of space)
Bedrock ledge slopes down to lower corner of limestone block, thus closing space at the bottom.
Height At back against E-W bedrock ledge: $\approx$.47 m.
front: .45 m.

SIFTING: yields 17 small (.3 mm diam) round flat beads ; $\approx$ 17 very small thin bone fragments (bird size); 2 chips basalt (or dacite?); assorted irregular limestone frags. pinkish and/or yellowish tints spots; 1 smooth shiny pebble; 1 round quartz pebble; 5 small ceramic particles and 1 small rim fragment; few small grey mud spots
SEVERAL more beads, bone frags. found 28/VIII/80 going through sifted pile; Sifted material consists of very fine (small & concentrated) limestone particles, chips, flakes, to larger frags.)